

SOCIAL NORMS AND JUNGLE JUSTICE IN IKOT EKPENE LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA, AKWA IBOM STATE, NIGERIA.

Abasiono Bassey Udofia
University of Uyo, Uyo
08056478892

Abstract

The criminal justice system is legally designated with the task of delivering justice to alleged criminals. Yet, jungle justice thrives, increasingly becoming a preferred option amongst Nigerians. The study aimed to examine the influence of social norms on the execution of jungle justice in Ikot Ekpene, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. The study employed the Convergence Parallel Design and adopted the Subculture of Violence Theory. Also, quantitative and qualitative tools – questionnaires and key informant interviews (KII) were employed to see points of convergence or divergence and to boost the overall reliability of the study. Qualitative results obtained from 12 participants were analysed thematically while the quantitative results obtained from 766 respondents were analyzed using Chi-square and tested at 0.5 level of significance. Both methods yielded complementary results. The study indicated that social norms obtainable in the locale impacted the execution of jungle justice. The normalization of the use of corporal punishment against general antisocial behaviour, the desire for quick retribution, viewing jungle justice as being fair, the “Agwo Annang ade Agwo uko” (an Annang person is a brave person) philosophy, the customary welding of machete amongst others is shown to influence jungle justice. From the findings, it is recommended that guardians should seldom use harsh corporal punishment against general delinquent behaviour as it only socializes individuals into the culture of violence. Community leaders should more actively discourage support and participation in jungle justice, forming local committees tasked with the responsibility of offering violence-free-first-aid to alleged criminals.

Keywords: Social norms, jungle justice, quick justice, and Ikot Ekpene

Introduction

Nations are increasingly beset by numerous social vices, which have significant detrimental effects. It is particularly alarming when these vices encroach upon the fundamental rights of individuals, leading to a deterioration of social conditions. One notable social vice is Jungle Justice, which has garnered international attention due to its prevalence, particularly in the streets of developing countries. As defined by Peter (2014), Jungle Justice refers to a form of public extrajudicial execution in sub-Saharan Africa, where individuals accused of criminal behaviour are subjected to humiliation, physical assault, or even summary execution by an enraged mob or vigilantes.

The application of jungle justice legally referred to as corporal punishment and the use of violent and inhumane methods to address antisocial behaviour in Africa, particularly in

Nigeria, extends beyond individuals suspected of criminal activity. While African children are generally loved and valued by their parents, they frequently endure life-threatening physical violence as a form of discipline, including severe beatings, burns, and strangulation inflicted by adults (Akpan and Oluwamide, 2010). In Nigeria, it is common and often accepted for children at home and students in schools to be punished through methods such as caning, whipping with belts, slapping with bare hands, striking with objects like wooden spoons, and enduring prolonged periods of kneeling (Iguh and Nosike, 2011). Consequently, the treatment of actual or perceived offenders in a similar, albeit more extreme, manner serves as a reflection of these prevailing practices.

The absence of a credible justification has led to the identification of various factors contributing to this troubling phenomenon. Alemika and Chukwuma (2000) along with Rowan et al. (2020) have linked this disturbing trend to a dysfunctional judiciary and law enforcement system that has lost its credibility. It is widely recognized that numerous notorious criminals and habitual offenders have evaded incarceration by exploiting loopholes within the Criminal Justice System (CJS). Consequently, members of the public often resort to self-help measures, opting for capital punishment and summary execution of suspected criminals rather than entrusting them to a CJS perceived as complicit in criminal activities. Llori (2020) further argues that this issue is exacerbated by the Nigerian police's inadequate response times, which has led to the public assuming the role of informal community policing, frequently resulting in instances of jungle justice. The slow reaction of law enforcement, which sometimes allows mobs to carry out these violent acts, fosters the belief among perpetrators that inflicting harm or death upon suspected offenders is acceptable. Additional factors such as illiteracy, a lack of respect for human rights, historical precedents, and public anger have also been recognized as contributing to the increase in jungle justice incidents.

Cultural elements, such as social norms, appear to create a conducive environment for the spread of jungle justice in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. These cultural elements serve as influential forces within communities, shaping the thoughts, emotions, and behaviours of their members. This underscores the importance of connecting social norms to the phenomenon of jungle justice which this study examined.

Statement of the Problem

The responsibility of administering justice to individuals who have committed crimes, or are believed to have done so, lies within the framework of the criminal justice system. This system is fundamentally based on two key principles: the recognition of certain rights for criminals and the necessity for criminal behaviour to be prosecuted and penalized by established laws. In alignment with International Best Practices, the Nigerian Constitution of 1999 (as amended) enshrines the right to human dignity and the right to a fair hearing in sections 34 and 36, respectively. Regardless of the severity of the alleged offence, the law maintains that every individual accused of a crime is entitled to a fair hearing, with the punishment imposed only upon a finding of guilt.

To support this framework, Nigeria has established various institutions, including the Police, Judiciary, and Correctional Centres, which are distributed throughout the states of the country. Furthermore, these institutions are equipped with both material and human

resources. Such measures are intended to ensure the effective functioning of these entities, facilitate public access to their services, and promote the prompt delivery of justice. It is concerning to observe the prevalence of a form of justice referred to as Jungle Justice, particularly in light of the social contract that exists within society. Nigeria, along with Cameroon, has unfortunately gained notoriety for having the highest incidence of jungle justice cases in Africa. The mere mention of jungle justice often brings Nigeria to mind. This troubling reputation has largely arisen from the actions of community and neighbourhood vigilantes, who enact brutal measures under the guise of delivering justice.

In response to security threats, individuals frequently resort to violence, opting to harm or lynch suspected offenders without allowing state security forces the opportunity to intervene (Llori, 2020). Victims of jungle justice are typically accused by enraged mobs of various offences, including rape, armed robbery, witchcraft, blasphemy, theft, and fraud, all without the benefit of a fair trial. Moreover, Onwuatuegwu and Nwagu (2020) have expressed concern over the inhumane nature of such actions, as an angry mob can swiftly pursue an accused individual at the mere utterance of an allegation, subjecting them to severe physical harm, ultimately resulting in the death of someone who has not been proven guilty of the alleged crime.

In Nigeria, while a clear pathway to justice is established, it has frequently been overshadowed. Various scholars have explored the phenomenon of jungle justice, attributing it to factors such as ignorance, low literacy levels, a failing and exploitative economy, hunger, frustration, and numerous other social, economic, and political influences (Operah and Okoko 2021, Ruwan *et al.* 2020, Olalekan 2017, and Adeleke 2017). A significant body of research has criticized the Criminal Justice System (CJS), labelling it as dysfunctional, yet there is a notable lack of studies focusing on Ikot Ekpene Local Government Area, where the issue of jungle justice is prevalent. Beyond the previously mentioned risk factors, particularly the erosion of public trust in the criminal justice system, what factors have contributed to the persistence of this form of justice, making it a preferred choice for many Nigerians? Is the prevalence of jungle justice attributed to entrenched social norms and customs? This study aims to address this gap in the literature by critically examining the influence of social norms on this form of justice in Ikot Ekpene Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

Objective of the Study

The objective of this was to examine the roles of social norms in the perpetuation of jungle justice in Ikot Ekpene Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

Hypothesis of the Study

Ho: There is no association between social norms and the execution of jungle justice in Ikot Ekpene Local Government Area.

Literature Review

The Concept of Jungle Justice

Jungle justice is neither a recent concept nor an unprecedented phenomenon globally, particularly in Africa. Salihu and Gholami (2018), referencing Arnold (2017), Osasona (2016), Adu-Gyamfi (2014), and Huggins (1991), contend that the notion of jungle or mob justice has existed alongside the criminal justice system itself. It was notably prevalent in the

United States during the 1860s amid the American Civil War, was common among Indigenous populations in the 1920s, and has recently become a familiar term in various African nations, especially Nigeria, Ghana, Cameroon, Kenya, Tanzania, South Africa, and Uganda.

As noted by Luke (2013) and cited by Obarisiagbon (2018), terms such as mob justice, instant justice, street justice, and jungle law serve as alternative expressions for jungle justice, all describing scenarios in which a group of individuals, disregarding legal protocols, administers punishment to those suspected of serious crimes. In a similar vein, Obarisiagbon (2018) characterizes jungle justice as the act of punishing a suspected offender by individuals who do not possess the legal authority to execute such actions.

Chima (2016) articulates the act as a brutal infringement upon the essential human rights of a suspected criminal, who is frequently subjected to humiliation, torture, and even set on fire by a mob that derives pleasure and satisfaction from witnessing what they perceive as justice being served. Ilori (2020) provides a more detailed perspective, asserting that jungle justice encompasses the actions of ethnic and neighbourhood vigilante groups that often create horrific spectacles in their efforts to safeguard the lives and properties of community members.

According to Yeboah-Assiamah and Kyeremeh (2014), jungle justice can involve crowds ranging from a few individuals to hundreds, all expressing their desire for justice through their actions. They further observe that mobs employ various weapons, including stones, blocks, sticks, iron rods, and other metallic objects, with their actions varying from spontaneous outbursts to premeditated assaults. Adinkrah (2015), in his examination of violent behaviors and jungle justice, notes that such acts of violence are predominantly carried out by male members of the community, who seek to protect their neighborhoods from antisocial conduct. This suggests that men are more actively involved in mob violence compared to women, who may participate only occasionally.

Ruwan *et al.* (2020) noted that such situations are marked by intense anger, noise, and demands for the punishment of the accused, who is often denied the chance to defend themselves. As emotions escalate and tensions rise, individuals within the mob tend to lose their self-control, self-awareness, and sense of personal accountability, becoming irrational and responding solely to the impulses of the agitated crowd (Schweingraber, 2000). Onwuatuegwu and Nwagu (2020) further support this view, suggesting that a key aspect of mob justice is the evident emotional and psychological instability displayed by those who engage in violent actions against the vulnerable individual caught in the turmoil. Abdulwahab (2016) highlights an even more troubling aspect: individuals who were not witnesses to the alleged offense and possess little knowledge of the events eagerly participate in the assault and lynching of the accused. As summarized by Operah and Okoko (2021), such incidents are clearly spontaneous, disorderly, chaotic, and defiant.

A comprehensive examination of definitions, in conjunction with the insights of Yeboah-Assiamah and Kyeremeh (2014), reveals that the phenomenon of jungle justice, also referred to as mob justice, is characterized by the following features:

a. The actions are executed by a relatively small group, typically numbering from a few individuals to several hundred. Initially, the involvement may be limited, but as tensions escalate, participation tends to increase.

b. The primary objective of these actions is to deter potential offenders and to signal to

the community that the area is a "no-go zone for criminals."

c. Such actions may be either premeditated or spontaneous.

d. The execution of these acts involves the application of physical force, indicating that mob justice is inherently violent.

e. The individuals engaging in these acts are predominantly male, with a smaller number of females, utilizing various weapons such as hand slaps, sticks, stones, and cutlasses to inflict harm.

f. The occurrence of jungle justice serves as a reflection of the public's discontent with the prevailing security and justice systems

Trend, Prevalence and Patterns of Jungle Justice in Nigeria

The existence of the Criminal Justice System, along with the enshrinement of the Right to Life, the Right to Human Dignity, and the Right to Fair Hearing in sections 33, 34, and 36 of the Nigerian Constitution, might lead one to assert that jungle or mob justice is unwarranted in Nigeria. However, Onwuaturgwu and Nwagu (2020) contend that the years in Nigeria have witnessed a troubling rise in incidents of jungle justice, a brutal practice that has resulted in the deaths of individuals merely accused of crimes.

The normalization of violence within our society has become a troubling cultural phenomenon. With each passing day, the Nigerian populace appears increasingly desensitized to acts of violence, largely due to the pervasive exposure to violent incidents throughout the country, including terrorism, banditry, secessionism, and the activities of 'unknown gunmen', riots, and social unrest. According to Peterside (2022), this ongoing exposure has led to a deterioration in our collective sense of decency, humanity, and appreciation for life. Furthermore, Nwakpu *et al.* (2020) highlight that the media in Nigeria is inundated daily with graphic images and videos depicting cases of jungle justice, making it impossible for any media consumer to deny the prevalence of such occurrences, whether nearby or far away. In a similar vein, many, including Nwakpu and Ogbodo (2018), assert that the situation has deteriorated to such an extent that incidents of punishment or death by jungle justice have become commonplace, frequently shared across social media platforms.

A 2014 survey referenced by Premium Times revealed that 43 percent of Nigerians have personally observed a mob attack or instances of jungle justice. Additionally, a report from Daily Trust dated October 3, 2021, noted that between January and November 2020, there were 83 recorded incidents of jungle justice nationwide, with 107 individuals lynched by angry mobs from January to September 2021. The report further indicates that 20 out of 190 victims were subjected to having tyres soaked in petrol placed around them and subsequently set on fire, while the remainder often suffered torture leading to death. Another Daily Trust report from June 3, 2022, highlighted that in May 2022 alone, Nigeria experienced 32 cases of jungle justice, all marked by brutal treatment. While some observers express pity during these acts of violence, others appear to take pleasure in the suffering. Ruwan *et al.* (2020) contend that the prevalence of this issue has fostered the perception that jungle justice is unique to Nigeria. Although this social problem is present across various states in the federation, Obarisiagbon (2018) emphasizes that the southern region of Nigeria has been particularly affected.

The activities of vigilante groups have significantly contributed to crime reduction and control; however, these efforts are frequently overshadowed by instances of jungle

justice. Ilori (2020) highlights prominent examples, such as the Oodua People's Congress in the South West and the Bakassi Boys in the South East of Nigeria. Reports from Human Rights Watch (HRW), the Center for Law Enforcement Education (CLEEN) (2002), and the Journal of Democracy and Development (2002) indicate that the Bakassi Boys have engaged in numerous extrajudicial killings and acts of torture against suspected criminals, often neglecting to hand them over to the criminal justice system. A notable incident occurred on May 29, 2001, in Onitsha, where the Bakassi Boys killed thirty-six alleged armed robbers using axes and machetes, subsequently mutilating and incinerating their bodies. Furthermore, a report by the Immigration and Refugee Board of Canada (2006), referencing articles from Vanguard (November 18, 2005) and This Day (August 30, 2005), claimed that the Bakassi Boys murdered twenty individuals and unlawfully detained thirty-seven suspected criminals in a poorly ventilated cell, resulting in the suffocation deaths of twenty-seven detainees in Abia State. The unlawful detention, mutilation, torture, and public execution of victims are often justified by "fabricated evidence, evidence obtained through torture, and a complete lack of evidence" (HRW and CLEEN, 2002).

The phenomenon of instant justice in Nigeria is not solely attributed to members of vigilante groups. In fact, the broader Nigerian society has played a significant role in fostering this practice, as evidenced by various studies and media reports. A notable example occurred on September 18, 2021, in Tangaza, Sokoto State, where an enraged mob stormed the local police station, overpowering law enforcement to kill 13 detained bandits and subsequently set their bodies ablaze (Daily Trust, Oct 03, 2021). Furthermore, the incident on May 12, 2022, in Sokoto challenges the notion that such acts are exclusively perpetrated by the uneducated. On that day, a student from Shehu Shagari College of Education was brutally beaten, stoned, and burned alive by her peers, who accused her of blasphemy against the Prophet Mohammed (Aderounmu, 2022).

The scourge of jungle justice has also victimized innocent individuals. As highlighted by Ruwan et al. (2020), the tragic execution of four undergraduate students from the University of Port Harcourt remains etched in the memories of many Nigerians. These students were subjected to necklace lynching and killed on October 4, 2012, after being falsely accused of theft in the Allu community of Rivers State. Similarly, Akpaekong (2021) reported the harrowing case of an innocent woman who was tortured to death on September 2, 2021, in Urua Okpokpo market, Akwa Ibom State, for allegedly stealing 2,500 Naira from a shop selling garri (cassava flakes). Despite her desperate pleas for innocence, the mob insisted on her execution. Tragically, the missing money was later discovered in the very shop, but by then, it was too late for her.

On March 25, 2020, a suspected armed robber encountered his fate at Itam market, located off Ikot Ekpene road in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, as reported by Onuegbu (2022) in Vanguard newspaper. Following an alleged robbery of a woman inside a tricycle, during which she was forcefully ejected by his accomplices, bystanders raised an alarm. This prompted members of the public to join in the pursuit, resulting in the capture of one gang member, who was subsequently beaten and set ablaze within the tricycle. A similar incident was documented by Emanuel (2021) in Vanguard newspaper, detailing how a group of alleged specialized point-of-sale (POS) robbers met their demise on Wednesday, August 8, 2021. After a failed robbery attempt on a POS attendant, who promptly alerted others, the robbers were chased, subdued, and ultimately set on fire by enraged youths in Ikot Oku Ikono,

Uyo, Akwa Ibom State. Additionally, in Lagos State, suspected traffic robbers were apprehended, severely beaten, and lynched by an irate mob on the Apapa/Mile 2 road during their criminal activity (Lambo, 2021).

Theoretical Framework

Subculture of Violence Theory

This theory was formulated in 1967 by Franco Ferracuti and Melvin Wolfgang, following their independent investigations into crime and violence, particularly within urban environments. Wolfgang and Ferracuti aimed to elucidate the reasons behind the elevated rates of violent crime and aggressive behaviour observed in certain communities or subcultures compared to others, specifically addressing why individuals in particular cultural contexts are more inclined to resort to violence than those in different cultural settings.

The core premise of the Subculture of Violence Theory posits that certain cultures, often found in economically disadvantaged urban areas, possess values, beliefs, and norms that not only normalize but also promote the use of violence as a reaction to perceived threats or injustices. Within such a subculture, an individual may be regarded as weak if they fail to retaliate or respond violently when confronted, thereby internalizing the culture of violence. Furthermore, the theory suggests that individuals who partake in these violent acts do not experience feelings of guilt, as such behaviours are perceived as normalized within their cultural milieu. They are simply perpetuating a learned pattern of violence that is transmitted across generations.

When applying this theoretical perspective to the study, it can be argued that the immediate, physical, and brutal treatment inflicted upon crime suspects by a crowd, although labelled as criminal in Nigeria, may not significantly differ from the values, norms, and practices prevalent in the society that socializes its members. Actions taken by crowds, such as jungle justice, should not be hastily dismissed as mere irrational behaviour or a form of contagion. Rather, these actions may represent a visible manifestation of the beliefs held by individual crowd members and can be perpetuated and passed down to future generations through various forms of communication and social interaction (including interactions with friends, neighbours, acquaintances, and social media). This process provides a platform for potential offenders to adopt the perceptions and justifications for such actions, as well as the norms that support violations of the law, ultimately leading to the enactment of these behaviours when a crime scene presents itself.

Methodology

The study adopted the Convergent Parallel Design. It employed both qualitative and quantitative methods. The Cross sectional Survey was used because it fits a mixed method approach. The research was conducted in Ikot Ekpene Local government area also known as the Raffia City. It is a famous town in Akwa Ibom- a south southern state in Nigeria. This locale is a commercial hub known to trade majorly on products of raffia such as raffia fibers, which are transformed into shoes, hats, clothes, and Palm products such as palm oil and palm kernel. The LGA is made up of two clans (Ikot Ekpene Urban and Amanyam District), eleven wards and 45 villages and is majorly inhabited by the Annang ethnic group who speak the Annang dialect. Ikot Ekpene Urban has 27 villages (Abak Oko, Abiakpo Edem Idim, Abiakpo Ikot Essien, Akanaan, Ibiakpan, Ibiakpan Ikot, Ibiakpan Nto Akan, Ibiakpo Edem Idim, Ibong

Nto Akan, Ifuho, Ikot Abia Idem, Ikot Idem, Ikot Inyang, Ikot Obong Edong, Ikot Otu, Ikot-Ekpene-Village, Ikotobio Okpon, Itak Ikot Udo-Okop, Ndem Ekpot, Nkap Ikot Obio Ebok, Nsiak, Obioekere, Uruk Uso, Utu Edem Usung, Utu Ikot Ekpenyong, Utu Ikot Essien and Utu Ikpe) while the Amanyam district houses 18 villages (Abak Ifia, Abiakpan Ikot Irem, Abiakpo Ntak-Inyang, Adaratak, Ata Essien Mbiaso, Ibong Ikot Akan, Ikot Akpan-Abia, Ikot Ediet, Ikot Enwang, Ikot Obong Otoro, Ikot Osura, Ikot Out, Ikot uboh, Ikot Udo Osung, Mbiaso Ikot Uso-udo, Mbiaso Nto-Obio Ekong, Nbo Obodom Ibiaso and Nyara Enyin-Ntong Uno). Jungle justice is not a novel subject matter in the terrain. Residents of Ikot Ekpene who were between the ages of 18 and above who had witnessed jungle justice constituted the population of the study. Nevertheless, the LGA according to the 2006 population census had a population of 143,077 and 220,911 as projected at 3.2% growth rate.

The study adopted both qualitative and quantitative sample and sampling techniques. Qualitative research lays premium on quality over quantity. The study used a sample size of 12 which was determined by thematic saturation. Due to the relatively sensitive nature of the research topic, the researcher employed purposive sampling technique to select few respondents and then employed the snowball sampling technique to reach the sample size. Also, with a measure of ease, the snowball sampling technique enabled the researcher identify those who had actually witnessed jungle justice. However, for the quantitative aspect of the study, the researcher targeted a sample of 784 (but used 766) respondents who necessarily were not actual eye witnesses of jungle justice but knowledgeable about it. This sample size was determined using the Proportion of the Population being 0.5, a confidence interval of 95% and an error margin of 3.5%.

Cluster, Simple and Systematic random sampling technique were employed. The LGA was divided into clusters of villages being 45. Using Simple Random sampling technique, nine villages were randomly selected. The researcher further employed Systematic Random sampling technique to draw 87 respondents from each of the randomly selected villages. This was made possible given the housing units from which at most two respondents were selected after every two housing units where practicable. Key Informant interviews (KII) and Questionnaire were used to obtain primary data from respondents of the study. KII was appropriate because it afforded the researcher an opportunity to obtain information from a relatively wide range of people, especially community leaders, residents, etc who had first-hand knowledge about the practice of jungle justice within their milieu. The use of Questionnaires complemented the former, and aided the researcher to obtain relevant quantitative data for the study from respondents.

Interview schedule and questionnaire were developed and employed. For the interview guide, a set of questions were administered with room for follow-ups and free discussion. Analysis of the personal characteristics of respondents were mainly descriptive using statistical tools such as simple percentages. After transcription, responses of the respondents in relation to the interviews were analyzed thematically. The main quantitative data (responses) were analyzed with the use of Chi-square.

Findings

Hypothesis

- a) Ho: There is no association between social norms and the execution of jungle justice in Ikot Ekpene LGA;

Table 1: Test of Hypothesis

FO	FE	(FO-FE)	(FO-FE) ²	(FO-FE) ² /FE
2,263	323.28	1,939.72	3,762,513.69	11,638.56
2357	336.81	2,020.19	4,081,167.64	12,117.12
426	60.86	365.14	133,327.22	2,190.72
316	45.14	270.86	73,365.14	1,625.28
				Σ = 27,571.68

Source: Field data (2023)

The chi-square calculated (X^2_{cal}) value = 27,571.68

The table value = $(r - 1)(C - 1)$

$(4 - 1)(7 - 1) = 3(6) = 18$

Degree of freedom (D/F) = 18

Degree of freedom at the level of 0.05 significance = 30.144

Decision: Since the chi-square calculated (X^2_{cal}) value (27,571.68) as shown on table 4.12 is greater than the table X^2 value (30.144), we reject the Null hypothesis (H_0) which states that social norms does not impact on the execution of jungle justice in Ikot Ekpene LGA at a D/F of 0.05 and accept the Alternate Hypothesis (H_1). We are 95% confident of this decision being right.

Results from Key Informants Interview (KII)

The results of the key Informant Interview yielded few themes

Theme One:

Acceptability and Socialization

This theme pertains to what the norm is with regards to the use of corporal punishments against general antisocial behavior and its impact on the treatment given to alleged criminals. When asked on this, most of the participants shared the following views;

P6: “Most people in this area including myself believe in the saying...spare the rod and spoil the child. So we flog our children seriously when they misbehave especially when he or she does what is very bad. This is exactly what we do to criminals in much greater degree. The criminal is being beaten to death or he is handed over to the police after he has seriously been punished”.

P2: “Who no sabi say them go seriously treat your matters if you misbehave or say you go steal. Na wetin we born come see. Our Parents been the flog us seriously with belt or spank you with hands, or just wound us small for body when we do bad not to talk of say them catch thief...your own don finish be that”.

P1: “In this our community, if somebody do what is not good, even it is my own child, we go punish him either by using cane, kneeling down till e start to shake, or just beat him mercilessly so that next time, he will not try it. To me, since we have this kind of background, we do not spare a thief or anybody who wants to make life harder for us. Community people who catch him will make sure that he feels pains there and then”.

Theme Two:

Desire to Help/ Reciprocate help

The articulations of the study participants showed that the desire to help or reciprocate help especially to people who are held in esteem in the community is a risk factor of jungle justice. In this regards, participants expressed thus;

P12: “People generally want to assist the victim to recover his property and in the process, at least, the criminal is unavoidably beaten and at times punished to death”.

P10: “let's say you were robbed by thieves who snatched your motorcycle. Upon raising an alarm, people responded, came out in good number, ran after the thieves, caught, beat-up and overpowered them and recovered your motorcycle. If same happens to another person afterwards, and he raises an alarm as you did when you fell a victim, what will you do? won't you assist?”.

P1: “If someone shouts thief o thief o for this market for example, it is expected that people around would be their brother's keeper, especially if he is not anyhow person, by pursuing the criminal to get back what he stole and give him the beatings that he was looking for and sometimes, make him to go naked round the market and even burn him. That is the expected action and reaction”.

Theme Three

Flare for Quick Retribution:

This theme relates to the participants desire for instant punishment to be meted out to crime suspects at the spot. The participants expressed their views thus;

P8: “Ukeed mkpo anem naàgha afiopo do, ufon owo ika bodise ibaaha (it is satisfying to act in the heat of a matter, there is no need to go to the police)... ado ubiad ini (it is waste of time)”.

P11: “We like it there and then. It makes more sense that way instead of following one long process”.

Theme Four

Desire to Display Courage:

This theme pertains to local customs that act as risk factor to the execution of jungle justice within the participants' locale. The participants shared their views thus;

P3: “It is customary for a true Ikot Ekpene person, an Annang man, to have a machete and to go about with it at times. An average Annang man is conscious of living up to the philosophy; Agwo Annang ade Agwo uko (an Annang man is a courageous person). Defending one's self with machete is considered as an act of courage. So when there is a dispute, a fight or when something like what we are discussing now (alleged crime) comes up, you see people quickly bringing out their matches and other weapons to chase the accused and when he is caught they deform him and butcher him into pieces”.

P7: “when provoked, an Annang person especially those in the interior part are fond of drawing out their matches which they customarily possess in response to perceived threats. In my little opinion and little observation, the possession of machetes and bringing it out when there is a threat as custom demands makes us somehow violent in the way we react to a person who is accused of a crime or one who is caught on the scene”.

Discussion of Findings

The thrust of this study was to examine the impact of cultural factors on jungle justice in Ikot Ekpene, Akwa Ibom state, Nigeria. The findings of this research has brought to bear that there exist a nexus between cultural factors (social norms, customs and perception) and the execution of jungle justice. From the data collected through questionnaires and KII, the answer to the first research question and hypothesis was identified. Findings from table 1 showed that social norms impacts on the execution of jungle justice in Ikot Ekpene, Akwa Ibom state, Nigeria. From the data obtained, it was discovered that people in the locale cherished quick retribution for anti-social behaviour, were not hesitant to meet out inhuman

treatment against alleged criminals, given also an atmosphere where support and participation in jungle justice was not actively discouraged by community leaders. These findings corroborates the works of Miller (2007) and Gershoff (2008) who on the basis of their study argued that people who grow up in an environment where slapping, spanking, from adults appears to be the norm, where the use of harsh physical punishment is normalized, are indirectly groomed into behaving aggressively in later life and were more likely to use physical violence during adulthood against others, and more so, resort to violent crimes.

Conclusion

The Nexus between cultural factors and execution of jungle justice cannot be overemphasized. This study has evidently brought to bear that social norms has direct impact on the lingering problem of instant mob or jungle justice. Although this problem may primarily have been born out of perceived or actual corruption of the Criminal Justice System in Nigeria and the chain reaction - subsequent distrust in the institution, the act has actually become a learned behaviour, something people do because that is the way it is done.

Recommendations

On the basis of the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made;

- 1) Parents and guardians should seldom use harsh corporal punishment against general delinquent behaviour as it only socializes individuals into the culture of violence as an accepted norm.
- 2) Community leaders should more actively discourage support and participation in jungle justice, forming local committees tasked with the responsibility of offering violence-free-first-aid to alleged criminals.

References

- Abdulwahab, A. (2016). Jungle Justice: Law and human rights. <https://www.Vanguard.com> (Retrieved on January 02, 2022).
- Aderounmu, (2022). Jungle Justice and the Need for National Orientation(1). <https://buisnessday.ng/opinion/article/Jungle-Justice-and-the-need-for-national-orientation-1/>
- Adinkrah, M. (2001). When parents kill: An analysis of filicides in Fiji. *International Journal of Offender Therapy and Comparative Criminology*, 45 144-158.
- Akpan, N. and Oluwabamide, A. (2010). The menace of child abuse in Nigeria: A case study of the street hawking in Uyo, Akwalbom state. *Journal of Social Science*, 3 189-192.
- Alimeka, E. and Chukuma, I. (2000). *Police Community Violence in Nigeria*. Lagos: Center for Law Enforcement Education and National Human Rights Commission.
- Chima, J. (2016). Jungle Justice in Nigeria or elsewhere. <https://www.linkedin.com/pluse/jungle-justice-Nigeria> (Retrieved on March 22, 2022).
- Human Rights Watch (HWR) and Center for Law Enforcement Education (CLEEN) (2002). "Nigeria. The Bakassi Boys: The legitimization of Murder and Torture" <https://hrwatch.org/reports/2002/nigeria2/nigeria0502.pdf> (Retrieved on March 26, 2022).

- Iguh, N. and Nosike, O. (2011). An examination of the child rights protection and corporal punishment in Nigeria. NamdiAzikiwe. *University Journal of International Law and Jurisprudence*, 2 97-111.
- Llori, A. (2020). Jungle justice in Lagos metropolice, Nigeria. *International Journal of Sociology and Anthropology*, 12(3): 59-66.
- Miller, C. (2007). Democratization, international knowledge institutions and global governance. *Governance*, 20(2) 325-357.
- Nwakpu, E., Ogbodo, J. (2018). Media depiction of sufferers/ victims of boko haram attacks in Nigeria and audience response. *International Journal of International Relations, Media and Mass Communication Studies*, 4(4) 1-15.
- Nwakpu, E., Ogbodo, J., Nwakpu, I. and Oyeleke, A. (2020). Spectators of suffering: Witnessing victims of jungle justices on social media. *Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences*, 11(1) 1-13.
- Obarisiagbon, E. (2018). Caught, clubbed and burnt: Criminological reflections on the incidence of jungle justice in Benin metropolis, Southern Nigeria. *International Journal of Arts and Humanities (IJAH) Ethiopia*, 7(3): 26.
- Olalekan, O. (2017). Jungle Justice: a hopeless people's reaction to an effective government <https://venturesafrica.com/Jungle-Justice-is-a-sign-of-helplessness> (Retrieved on May 4, 2022).
- Onuegbu, C. (2022). Angry mob sets suspected armed robbers ablaze in Akwa Ibom. <https://www.vanguardngr.com/2022/03/angry-mob-sets-suspected-armed-robbers-ablaze-in-akwa-ibom/>(Retrieved on June 6, 2022).
- Onwuatuogwu, I. and Nwagu, N. (2020). Jungle justice: A peak of failure of humanity. *International Journal of Scientific Research in Essay and Case Studies*, 1(1): 12-20.
- Oparah, O., and Okoko, C. (2021). Mob action or 'jungle justice': A contextual security imperative. *International Journal of Arts and Social Sciences*, 1(2) 146-150.
- Peterside, D. (2020) Spread of Mob Justice in Nigeria. <https://www.thecable.ng/spread-of-mob-justice-in-Nigeria/>(Retrieved on February 8, 2023).
- Ruwan, I., Ogechukwu, O., Jose, C., Fadare, G. and Garba, M. (2020). Appraisal of jungle justice on the incidence of crime in Nigeria. Kampala International University (KIU). *Journal of Social Sciences*, 6(3): 135-145.
- Salihu, H and Gholami, H. (2018). Mob justice, corrupt and unproductive justice system in Nigeria: An empirical analysis. *International Journal of Law, Crime and Justice*, 55: 40-51.
- Schweingraber, D. (2000). Escalated force: Sociology's contribution to repressive police tactics. *The Sociology Quarterly*, 41(3) 371-389.
- Yeboah-Assiamah and Kyeremeh (2014). A critical assessment of public administration and civil disobedience in developing African democracies: an international analysis of mob justice in Ghana. *Journal of Law, Policy and Globalization*, 28 1-11.

